

Vibratory polishing effects on passivity of 304L stainless steel surfaces

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Abstract

Surface spectroscopy analysis and electrochemistry were applied to study the effects of surface preparation by vibratory polishing on the passivity of stainless steel 304L surfaces. Compared to grinding by traditional mechanical polishing, vibratory polishing promotes the enrichment of Cr(III) oxide and hydroxide species in the duplex chemical structure of the surface native oxide film by enhancing selective Fe oxidation and dissolution. As a result, spontaneous passivity, tested in aggressive sulfuric acid electrolyte, is enhanced. However, in the absence of enrichment in Mo(IV) and Mo(VI) species in the passive film, the Cr enrichment does not enhance passivity upon anodic polarization nor increase the resistance to Cl-induced passivity breakdown and initiation of localized corrosion in accelerated testing conditions. The results provide comprehensive insight into the mechanisms underlying the passivity enhancement of stainless steel by surface engineering.

Keywords:

Surface treatment; Vibratory polishing; Stainless steel; Oxide film; Passivity; Localized corrosion

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1. Introduction

Mechanical polishing with the traditional method in which the sample is ground against a (most usually) rotating polishing cloth is a common practice for surface preparation finish applied for corrosion studies of metals and alloys such as stainless steels (SS) [1–6]. Although there is a variety of user-dependent procedures with the sample held by hand or with a holder, polishing plate rotating or not, and grinding particles of different types and grades, traditional mechanical polishing by grinding enables us to homogenize the surface by minimizing or eliminating the major morphological imperfections and dirt, and thus helps to produce more reproducible initial surface states. Additionally, other surface finishing methods such as vibratory polishing, high-temperature annealing in inert or reducing gas, and electropolishing can also be applied to improve the surface quality by removing, at least partially, the cold-work layer and better revealing the bulk microstructure at the topmost surface [6–11]. Among them, vibratory polishing is popular due to the user-friendly preparation method; the automated vibratory action creates friction to rob the sample with smoother surface grinding than with classical non-vibratory grinding [6,12,13]. For instance, vibratory polishing is a classically applied surface finish to examine the metal microstructure by electron back-scattered diffraction (EBSD) [3], owing to a thinner cold-work layer leftover than traditional mechanical polishing.

Recently, it was shown on 316L stainless steel that vibratory polishing could also modify the surface native oxide film and thereby improve corrosion resistance by enhancing passivity [12]. Compared to traditional mechanical polishing with grinding particles of the same nature and grade, the duplex structure of the surface native oxide typically reported for 316L [12], and other SS grades [6,13], was unchanged, but further enriched in Cr(III) oxide in the inner barrier layer and in Cr(III) hydroxide and Mo(IV/VI) oxides in the outer layer. As a result, the passivity provided

by this protective surface oxide film was promoted at the active-passive transition in acid solution, and the resistance to chloride-induced passivity breakdown was enhanced. It was also shown that, in order to expose the bulk alloy microstructure at the topmost surface, it was necessary to fully reconstruct the cold-worked layers leftover by traditional or vibratory finishing, for instance, by high-temperature annealing in a reducing hydrogen environment. However, this post-treatment resulted in the loss of the beneficial effects on passivity brought by the vibratory finish since reducing the initially modified, more protective native oxide.

Here, we report on the chemical structure and composition of the native oxide-covered surfaces obtained either by traditional (rotational) polishing or by vibratory polishing of austenitic Mo-free stainless steel (SS304L) surfaces, and we discuss the effects of the vibratory post-treatment on the passivation properties in sulfuric acid aqueous solution and resistance to chloride-induced passivity breakdown. State-of-the-art surface analysis by time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (ToF-SIMS) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was applied together with electrochemical analysis by potentiodynamic and potentiostatic polarization of the passivation properties. A comprehensive comparison with data obtained on SS316L surfaces allows us to discuss the relation between elemental enrichment in the protective surface oxide film and enhanced passivity and the effects that can be expected from the surface finish.

2. Materials and methods

Low carbon polycrystalline 304L stainless steel of Fe-18%Cr-10%Ni (wt.%) composition was used [14]. For the samples hereafter denoted TP (traditional polish), the surface was ground first with SiC paper down to 2400 grade and then with diamond suspensions of successive 6, 3, 1, and 0.25 μm grades. For the samples denoted VP (vibratory polish), the surface was further polished using a Vibrotech300 polisher for 5-6 hours at a vibration amplitude of 47 μm and frequency of

47 Hz. The same diamond suspension of 0.25 μm mixed in alcohol-based lubricant at a volume ratio of 1:1 was used as a polishing agent for the final stage of the TP procedure. After both procedures, the samples were rinsed in ultrasonicated baths of acetone, ethanol, and UP (ultra-pure) water (resistivity $> 18 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}$) for 5 minutes each. Filtered compressed air was used for drying. These TP [15–18] and VP [12] surface preparation procedures have been applied in previous studies.

Electrochemical measurements were performed in a 3-electrode electrochemical cell controlled by a Gamry 600 potentiostat, and repeated at least 3 times to ensure reproducibility. The reference electrode was a saturated Ag/AgCl electrode, the counter electrode was a gold coil, and the working electrode was the sample surface of a 2.09 cm^2 area delimited by a Viton O-ring. The electrolyte was a 0.05 M sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) aqueous solution prepared from UP chemicals (VWR) and water. Potentiodynamic polarization was performed to characterize the passivation behaviour. The i - E curves were recorded after stabilization for 30 minutes at open circuit potential (OCP), starting the potential scan (1 mV/s) from a cathodic vertex negative with respect to OCP until oxygen evolution. Potentiostatic polarization was used to test the resistance to Cl-induced passivity breakdown. After 15 minutes of stabilization at OCP in the chloride-free 0.05M H_2SO_4 electrolyte, a fixed passivation potential of 0.3 V_{SHE} was applied for 1 hour before incrementing the chloride concentration step-wise (0.1 M) every 10 minutes. The test was ended when the initiation of localized corrosion was observed. The adjusting chloride solution was prepared with NaCl (VWR) first dissolved in UP water.

A digital Keyence VHX-500 optical microscope with lens magnification of 100×1000 and 500×5000 and a CSI instruments Nano-observer AFM microscope were used to characterize the surface topography. AFM imaging was performed in non-contact mode with a silicon probe from

AppNano, USA, operating at a 50-70 kHz resonance frequency and with a cantilever spring constant of 1-5 N/m. The scanned images were converted into portable image format with the Gwyddion (64-bit) software [19] without further processing.

An IONTOF ToF-SIMS 5 spectrometer (base pressure of about 10^{-9} mbar) operating in dual-beam mode was used for depth profile elemental analysis of the native oxide-covered surfaces. Analysis was performed with a pulsed 25 KeV Bi^+ primary ion source delivering 1.2 pA of target current over a $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$ area, and interlaced with sputtering using a 0.5 keV Cs^+ beam delivering 20 nA of target current over a $300 \times 300 \mu\text{m}^2$ area. Both ion beams were at an angle of incidence of 45° with respect to the sample surface and aligned to ensure analysis from the centre of the sputtered crater. The Bi^+ primary ion flux was sufficiently low to ensure analysis in static SIMS conditions. Only negative ions were recorded because of their higher sensitivity to fragments coming from oxide matrices. The IONSPEC 6.5 software was used for data acquisition and post-processing.

A Thermo Electron ESCALAB 250 spectrometer (base pressure of 10^{-9} mbar) was used for XPS analysis of the surface composition and oxide film thickness. A monochromatized Al $\text{K}\alpha$ X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) was used, and the take-off angle of the analysed photoelectrons was 90° . Survey and high-resolution spectra were recorded with a pass energy of 100 and 20 eV, respectively, and a step size of 1 and 0.1 eV, respectively. The Avantage software was used for peak fitting [20]. The high-resolution Cr 2p_{3/2}, Fe 2p_{3/2}, Ni 2p_{3/2}, O 1s, and C 1s core-level spectra were reconstructed with specific self-consistent fitting parameters [12,21]. A set of constraints was applied to background subtraction (adjustable Shirley), binding energy (BE), full-width half maximum (FWHM), and line shape of peak components in order to achieve the most accurate and

consistent fit of the high-resolution spectra. Binding energies (BE) were calibrated by setting the C 1s signal corresponding to olefinic bonds ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$) at 285.0 eV.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Surface morphology

Figure 1 presents typical images of the TP and VP sample surfaces. The granular microstructure polycrystalline sample is not visible on the optical image of the TP surface (Figure 1a) due to the presence of the covering cold-work layer, but the surface is clean and homogenous at the microscopic level. Polishing lines are observed on the topmost surface measured by AFM (Figure 1b). They confirm the presence of a surface cold-work layer resulting from the TP surface preparation finish and homogeneously covering the polycrystalline microstructure. The R_a surface roughness measured by AFM is ~ 15 nm.

After the VP surface finish, polishing lines are still observed at the topmost surface, evidencing that a cold-work layer remains at the surface (Figure 1d). However, the underlying polycrystalline microstructure becomes apparent as seen by optical micrography (Figure 1c). Optical microscopy probing the surface over a larger depth than atomic force microscopy, the cold-work layer that remains from the VP surface finish is obviously thinner than that resulting from the TP surface finish. This is also reflected by the decrease of the R_a surface roughness measured by AFM to ~ 10 nm.

3.2. Passivation behaviour and resistance to passivity breakdown

Figure 2 compares the passivation behaviour of the TP and VP samples measured by potentiodynamic polarization performed in 0.05 M $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4(\text{aq})$ solution after 30 minutes of stabilization at OCP. The corrosion potentials of the TP and VP samples are $U_{\text{corr}} = -0.38$ and -0.33

V_{SHE} , respectively. The positive shift of the corrosion potential evidences the more noble character provided by the native oxide film formed on the VP sample and subsisting after modification resulting from immersion at OCP.

In the potential range between U_{corr} and $U_{corr} + 0.2$ V, no passivation peak, i.e., critical current, is measured, indicating spontaneous passivation at OCP. The corrosion current as well the current measured in this potential range are lower for the VP than for the TP SS304L sample. This indicates a more protecting character of the passive state obtained at OCP by immersion of the native oxide-covered surface obtained after VP pretreatment, which confirms the VP effect observed on SS316L surfaces [12]. However, as the potential increases in the passive domain, the anodic current of the VP SS304L sample becomes slightly higher than that of the TP SS304L sample, as confirmed by repeated measurements. This difference in anodic passive currents suggests that the beneficial effects of the VP pretreatment observed for the SS304L surfaces on the corrosion resistance at OCP are lost after anodic polarization as confirmed by potentiostatic polarization in the passive domain, as shown hereafter. As the transpassive domain is approached, the difference in passive behaviour between the TP and VP SS304L surfaces is attenuated, suggesting a similar rate of dissolution of chromium [12,15,22], also with no subsisting effects of the VP pretreatment.

Typical current transients measured upon anodic potentiostatic polarization in 0.05 M $H_2SO_4(aq)$ at +0.3 V_{SHE} are shown in Figure 3. After one hour of polarization in the Cl^- -free electrolyte, the Cl^- ion concentration was increased step-wise as marked. During the first 3600 s of passivation in the Cl^- -free solution, the current density dropped fast at the beginning and then levelled off continuously. This behaviour, typical of anodic passivation of stainless steel [12,15,22], shows that an increasingly protective anodic passive film is formed with time, however, without reaching

a stable steady-state in the time frame of the present experiments. No significant difference was observed in the current density for the TP and VP surfaces before chloride addition, showing the formation of similarly protective passive films at a potential corresponding to the medium range of the passive domain. We note that the beneficial VP effect observed on the passivity of SS316L surfaces in the same polarization conditions [12] is not reproduced on the present SS304L surfaces, possibly owing to the absence of Mo in the alloy and lack of VP-induced combined enrichment in Mo and Cr oxides in the passive film as discussed in the following part.

With Cl^- ions first added to reach a 0.1 M concentration, the current density of the TP surface continuously decreases first, following the same trend as in the absence of chlorides, and then increases sharply before increasing suddenly as soon as the chloride ion concentration is increased to 0.2 M. No anodic current spikes characteristic of depassivation/re-passivation events (i.e., metastable pitting) are observed, indicating that Cl^- -induced passivity breakdown is followed by the initiation of localized corrosion without self-repair of the passive film. The absence of metastable events observed prior to the initiation of stable localized corrosion on this SS304L sample-confirms that, due to the absence of Mo promoting the resistance to Cl^- -induced passivity breakdown and self-repair, SS304L poorly resists to localized corrosion.

In the case of VP SS304L surface, the current sharply and irreversibly increases, immediately after adding chloride ions to the concentration of 0.1 M. This indicates no beneficial effect of the VP pretreatment on both resistance to Cl^- -induced passivity breakdown and self-repair of passivity, despite the increased corrosion resistance observed at OCP. This contrasts with VP-pretreated SS316L surfaces on which enhancing effects of the VP pretreatment were observed [12]. Again, this suggests that the VP-induced increased enrichment in Cr oxide in the native oxide film (see below) cannot enhance the resistance to passivity breakdown and localized corrosion if not

combined with Mo enrichment of the surface, as observed on Cr-containing multi-principal element alloys for instance [23].

3.3. Duplex chemical structure of native oxide film

Figure 4 presents ToF-SIMS depth profiles measured on the TP and VP native oxide-covered surfaces. In Figures 4a, and 4d, the intensities of the secondary ions selected as characteristic of the covering oxide film (CrO_2^- , FeO_2^- , NiO^- and NiOH^-) and metallic substrate (Fe_2^- and Ni_2^-) are reported using a logarithmic scale, which puts emphasis on signals of low intensities. The metal/oxide interface was positioned at a sputtering time corresponding to approximately 80 % of the maximum intensity of the Fe_2^- signal [24]. By doing so, the metal/oxide interface is located at ~55 and ~60 s on the TP and VP samples, respectively. In both samples, the metallic substrate entered right after the metal/oxide interface exhibits a modified alloy region enriched in Ni close to the metal/oxide interface as indicated by a slight maximum of the Ni_2^- ion intensity. This enrichment, confirmed by XPS analysis, is typical of native oxide-covered SS surfaces [12,15,17,22].

The CrO_2^- , FeO_2^- , NiO^- , and NiOH^- ions all reach their maximum intensities in the outermost region corresponding to the oxide film covering the metal substrate. The CrO_2^- and FeO_2^- depth profiles are the most intense. In Figure 4b, where the plots are in linear scale, the FeO_2^- ion profile peaks before the CrO_2^- ion profile (at ~15 s vs. ~33 s). This sequence evidences that the native oxide film formed on the surface prepared by TP surface finish has a duplex layered structure, with iron and chromium concentrated in the outer and inner oxide layers, respectively, as observed on SS316L surfaces also prepared with TP surface finish [12,15,17,22]. The interface between the outer and inner oxide layers is located at ~22s, considering the median sputtering position between the two intensity maxima. This duplex chemical structure of the oxide film is also illustrated in

Figure 4c, where the $\text{CrO}_2^-/\text{FeO}_2^-$ intensity ratio markedly increases from the outer to inner regions of the surface oxide film. The markedly less intense NiO^- and NiOH^- ion profiles both peak in the inner region of the duplex oxide film, close to the metal/oxide interface (Figure 4a). They correspond to traces of nickel (hydro)oxide species, undetected by XPS, as shown below.

For the SS304L surface prepared with the VP surface finish (Figure 4e), the FeO_2^- ion profile also peaks before the CrO_2^- ion profile (at ~10 s vs. ~24 s), confirming a duplex chemical structure with an interface between outer and inner layers located at ~17s according to the median sputtering position between the two intensity maxima. Compared to the TP sample, the negative shift (towards shorter sputtering time) of the interface between the outer and inner layers, combined with the slight positive shift of the metal/oxide interface, suggests that the inner layer of the duplex native oxide could be thicker on the VP than on the TP sample. A comparison of Figures 4b and 4e also shows that the CrO_2^- ion profile peaks at a significantly higher intensity, and the FeO_2^- ion profile peaks at a significantly lower intensity for the VP sample than for the TP sample. These variations, also illustrated by the higher $\text{CrO}_2^-/\text{FeO}_2^-$ intensity ratio measured all through the oxide film region (Figure 4f), show that the VP surface finish promotes global chromium enrichment, balanced by iron depletion, of the native oxide film, an effect also observed on SS316L surfaces prepared by VP surface finish [12]. Regarding the NiO^- and NiOH^- ion profiles, Figure 4d shows that they peak in the inner and outer layers of the duplex oxide, respectively. Compared to the TP sample, the intensity of the NiOH^- ions in the inner layer is markedly decreased, whereas that of the NiO^- ions is increased, suggesting that the VP surface finish promotes the accumulation of anhydrous oxidized Ni species at trace level in the inner part of the oxide film.

3.4. Surface species identification

The high-resolution Fe 2p_{3/2}, Cr 2p_{3/2}, Ni 2p_{3/2}, and O 1s core-level spectra measured on the TP and VP samples are presented in Figure 5, and the binding energy (BE), full width at half maximum (FWHM), and relative intensity (RI) values obtained by peak fitting are compiled in Table 1. In the Fe 2p_{3/2} spectra, the peaks at 706.9 and 709.9 eV, the latter with broad FWHM, are assigned to a Fe⁰ (metal) component and a generic hydroxide/oxide/oxyhydroxide Fe³⁺ component, respectively [12,21]. The relative intensity of the Fe³⁺ component markedly decreases on the VP surface, showing that the oxidized iron species are relatively less, in agreement with the trend observed by ToF-SIMS. The presence of Cr⁰ (metal), Cr³⁺ (oxide), and Cr³⁺ (hydroxide) surface species are characterized by the peaks fitted at 574, 576/576.4, and 577/577.3 eV, respectively, in the Cr 2p_{3/2} spectra [21]. The total RI of the oxide and hydroxide components is slightly higher for the VP than for the TP surface. The Ni 2p_{3/2} core-level spectra could be fitted with the metallic component and its satellite for both surfaces, however, with no need to add oxide or hydroxide components. Thus, the low amount of oxidized nickel species detected by ToF-SIMS is below the detection limit of XPS. Three components at 530.1, 531.6, and 532.3 eV, assigned to oxide (O₂⁻), hydroxide (OH⁻), and water (H₂O) ligands in the oxide film, respectively, were used to fit the O 1s core-level spectra [15,21,25]. The component at 532.3 eV can also originate from surface contamination, including C=O double bonding. The OH⁻/O₂⁻ intensity ratio is 0.47 for the TP surface and 1.3 for the VP surface, suggesting higher global hydroxylation after the VP surface finish.

3.5. Oxide film thickness and surface composition

Table 2 compiles the values of the oxide film thickness and relative concentration in alloying elements of the oxide film and modified underlying alloy region calculated from the XPS data

applying a single-layer model of attenuation of the photoelectrons' intensities [12,15,16,21,22,26]. For the surface prepared with TP finish, the oxide film is 1.3 nm thick, which is close to reported values for native oxide films on SS316L and SS304L surfaces [12,15,27–30]. Major oxide constituent is iron (64 at%). However, the total chromium oxide and hydroxide content of 36 % shows that Cr is enriched compared to the bulk alloy concentration of 18 %. The trace amount of nickel oxide and hydroxide measured by ToF-SIMS cannot be quantified from XPS (< 0.5 %). In the modified alloy region underneath the oxide film, chromium is slightly depleted, nickel slightly enriched, and iron at the bulk level, indicating selective oxidation of Cr and Fe upon formation of the native oxide [12,15,16,30]).

For the surface prepared with VP finish, we calculate a thickness of 1.4 nm, similar to that for the TP surface if we consider the accuracy of the measurement. However, the Cr concentration in the oxide film increased (48 vs. 36 % for the TP surface), and the Fe concentration decreased (52 vs. 64 %), confirming the trend observed by ToF-SIMS. Ni remains below the detection limit. This effect of the VP surface finish in promoting the Cr oxide enrichment in the oxide film is similar, although less marked, to that obtained on SS316L surfaces, for which the increase was up to 63 Cr% [12]. In the modified alloy region underneath the oxide film, one observes the depletion in metallic iron (55 vs 73 % for the TP surface) balanced by the increase of the enrichment in Ni (27 vs. 13 %) and the decrease of the depletion in Cr (18 vs 14 %), indicating preferential consumption of iron. Again, this trend is like that observed on SS316L samples also prepared by VP pretreatment after TP surface preparation. It suggests that the VP pretreatment activates a fretting corrosion mechanism leading to preferential etching of iron.

In Table 3, we report the values obtained using a refined model of attenuation of the photoelectrons' intensities considering the duplex chemical structure of the oxide film observed

by ToF-SIMS. The generic Fe^{3+} (hydroxide/oxide/oxyhydroxide) and Cr^{3+} (hydroxide) species are assigned to the outer exchange layer of the duplex structure and the Cr^{3+} (oxide) species to the inner barrier layer, in agreement with previous work [16,22,26,30]. The minor concentration of the inner barrier layer in iron oxide species suggested by the ToF-SIMS depth profile is neglected. The concentration values of the modified alloy region obtained with this bilayer model are identical within the uncertainty to those obtained in the single-layer model; they are not reported in Table 3.

The total oxide film thickness of the TP sample is 1.3 nm, including a 0.9 nm thick outer layer and 0.4 nm inner layer, which meets the previous results of similar studies on SS316L surfaces prepared with a TP surface finish [12,15,17,22]. The relative concentrations of the outer layer are 84 % for generic Fe^{3+} (hydroxide/oxide/oxyhydroxide) species and 16 %, for the Cr^{3+} (hydroxide) species, indicating that the global Cr enrichment of the oxide film originates from the Cr^{3+} (oxide) species concentrated in the inner barrier layer. For the VP surface, the total oxide thickness is 1.5 nm, including a 0.9 nm thick outer layer and a 0.6 nm thick inner layer. The thickness of the outer layer is the same for the TP and VP surfaces, but there is a slight increase of the concentration in Cr^{3+} (hydroxide) species (20 vs. 16 %) resulting from the promoting effect of the VP pretreatment on the Cr enrichment. This promoting effect is also reflected by the increase in thickness (0.6 vs 0.4 nm) calculated for the inner barrier layer assumed to be constituted of 100 % Cr^{3+} (oxide) species.

These results indicate that the vibratory surface finish promotes the Cr enrichment of the native oxide film both in its inner region, resulting in the formation of a thicker inner barrier layer, and in its outer region, increasing the concentration of the exchange layer in more corrosion resistant chromium hydroxide. Like on SS316L surfaces, the Cr enrichment of the surface native oxide most

likely results from the preferential etching of iron, leaving nickel enriched in the underlying alloy region from which the reactive species were consumed. This enrichment is concentrated in the inner layer of the native oxide film, which can be expected to contribute to consolidate the protectiveness provided by this barrier layer where Fe-rich weak sites can form as a result of the lack of local supply of Cr upon initial growth of surface oxide film [31]. However, unlike on SS316L surfaces, there is no molybdenum in SS304L that can be enriched concomitantly in the native oxide film by the VP pretreatment, and thus reinforce the Fe-rich weak sites of protection like proposed based on surface analysis of the surface oxide films formed on Cr- and Mo-containing multi principal element alloys [32]. As a result, the corrosion resistance on the VP-pretreated SS304L surfaces is improved only after spontaneous passivation at OCP but not under anodic polarization where the driving force for Cl-induced passivity breakdown is higher.

4. Conclusion

It has been shown that, compared to traditional surface preparation finish by mechanical polishing, post-treatment by vibratory polishing improves the surface topology by decreasing the surface roughness and reducing the thickness of the cold-work layer leftover by grinding. Passivity in aggressive sulfuric acid solution is moderately enhanced and characterized by the shift of the corrosion potential towards a more noble character and the decrease of the current density at and immediately above open circuit potential. This enhancement of spontaneous passivity results from the increase of the Cr enrichment of the surface native oxide film. The duplex chemical structure of the protective oxide film is unchanged, however with a slight increase of the Cr(III) hydroxide concentration in the outer exchanged layer and an increase in thickness of the inner barrier layer, the latter reflecting the enrichment in more stable Cr(III) oxide species and the related consolidation of the Fe-rich weak sites of protection. Comparison with vibratory polishing effects

observed on SS316L surfaces shows that, in the absence of concomitant Mo enrichment of the native oxide film, the increase of the Cr enrichment produced by the vibratory surface finish on SS304L surfaces does not enhance anodic passivity nor increase the resistance to Cl-induced passivity breakdown in accelerated testing conditions of localized corrosion initiation.

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Declaration of interest statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Table 1

Table 1: Component peaks obtained from reconstruction of the XPS core-level spectra with binding energy (BE), full width at half maximum (FWHM), and relative intensity (RI) for TP and VP SS304L surfaces

Core level	peak	Assignment	TP			VP		
			BE (±0.1 eV)	FWHM (±0.1 eV)	RI (%)	BE (±0.1 eV)	FWHM (±0.1 eV)	RI (%)
Fe 2p _{3/2}	Fe ⁰	Metal	706.9	0.79	32	706.9	0.79	52
	Fe ⁺³	Oxide	709.9	3.3	68	709.9	3.1	48
Cr2p _{3/2}	Cr ⁰	Metal	574	1.31	33	574	1.31	30
	Cr ⁺³	Oxide	576	2	34	576.4	2	39
	Cr ⁺³	Hydroxide	577	2.7	33	577.3	2.7	31
Ni 2p _{3/2}	Ni ⁰	Metal	853	1.01	93	852.8	1.01	91.5
	Ni ⁰ (sat)	Ni Sat	859	3.6	7	859	3.6	8.5
O 1s	O ₂ ⁻	Oxide	530.1	1.0	55.4	530.1	1.1	37.8
	OH ⁻	Hydroxide	531.6	1.5	26.2	531.6	1.6	52.5
	H ₂ O	water	532.3	1.7	18.7	532.3	1.7	9.6

Table 2

Table: 2 Surface composition in alloying elements and oxide layer thickness as calculated from the XPS data with a single-layer model of photoelectron attenuation for SS304L surfaces and comparison with data obtained on SS316L surfaces.

Stage	Thickness d (±0.1 nm)	Relative concentration in alloying elements (±2 at.%)							
		Oxide layer				Modified alloy			
		Fe	Cr	Ni	Mo	Fe	Cr	Ni	Mo
TP SS304L	1.3	64	36	< 0.5	NA	73	14	13	NA
VP SS304L	1.4	52	48	< 0.5	NA	55	18	27	NA
TP SS316L [12]	1.4	58	39	< 0.5	3	63	10	25	2
VP SS316L [12]	1.3	30	63	< 0.5	7	50	13	35	2

Table 3

Table: 3 Oxide layer thickness and composition in alloying elements as calculated from the XPS data with a bilayer model for SS 304L surfaces and comparison with data obtained on SS316L surfaces. The composition of the inner layer is 100% Cr oxide.

Stage	Thickness d (± 0.1 nm)			Relative concentration in alloying elements of outer oxide layer (± 2 at.%)			
	Total	Outer layer	Inner layer	Fe	Cr	Ni	Mo
TP SS304L	1.3	0.9	0.4	84	16	< 0.5	NA
VP SS304L	1.5	0.9	0.6	80	20	< 0.5	NA
TP SS316L [12]	1.7	1.2	0.5	78	20	< 0.5	2
VP SS316L [12]	1.5	0.8	0.7	56	39	< 0.5	5

Figure 1

Figure 1: Surfaces of the (a,b) TP and (c,d) VP polycrystalline SS304L samples observed by (a,c) optical microscopy and (b,d) atomic force microscopy

Figure 2

Figure 2: Polarization curves of SS304L samples prepared with TP and VP surface finish recorded in 0.05 M H₂SO₄(aq) after 30 min stabilization at OCP (scan rate: 1 mV/s).

Figure 3

Figure 3 Passivation current transients of SS304L samples prepared with TP and VP surface finish recorded in 0.05 M H₂SO₄(aq) after 15 min stabilization at OCP. Anodic polarization at +0.3 V_{SHE} in the Cl-free base electrolyte for 60 min before step-wise addition of chloride ions every 10 min as marked.

Figure 4

Figure 4 ToF-SIMS depth profiles for (a-c) TP and (d-f) VP native oxide-covered SS304L surfaces

Figure 5

Figure 5 XPS high resolution spectra and peak fitting of (a,b) Fe 2p_{3/2}, (c,d) Cr 2p_{3/2}, (e,f) Ni 2p_{3/2} and (g,h) O 1s core-level regions for (a,c,e,g) TP and (b,d,f,h) VP SS304L samples

Figure captions

Figure 1: Surfaces of the (a,b) TP and (c,d) VP polycrystalline SS304L samples observed by (a,c) optical microscopy and (b,d) atomic force microscopy

Figure 2: Polarization curves of SS304L samples prepared with TP and VP surface finish recorded in 0.05 M H₂SO₄(aq) after 30 min stabilization at OCP (scan rate: 1 mV/s).

Figure 3 Passivation current transients of SS304L samples prepared with TP and VP surface finish recorded in 0.05 M H₂SO₄(aq) after 15 min stabilization at OCP. Anodic polarization at +0.3 V_{SHE} in the Cl-free base electrolyte for 60 min before step-wise addition of chloride ions every 10 min as marked.

Figure 4 ToF-SIMS depth profiles for (a-c) TP and (d-f) VP native oxide-covered SS304L surfaces

Figure 5 XPS high resolution spectra and peak fitting of (a,b) Fe 2p_{3/2}, (c,d) Cr 2p_{3/2}, (e,f) Ni 2p_{3/2} and (g,h) O 1s core-level regions for (a,c,e,g) TP and (b,d,f,h) VP SS304L samples